

IMPACT OF DIGITIZATION ON THE COMPETITIVENESS OF VITICULTURE ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

At this stage, Bulgaria has a ready and established strategy for digitization of agriculture, but there is no such strategy for the viticulture industry. I believe that the digitalization strategy of agriculture should be decomposed into separate sectoral strategies if we want an effective sectoral digitalization strategy in terms of achieving competitive development. Each branch of agriculture has its specifics, which must be reflected in the strategy for its digitalization, and that each of the strategies must be complemented with the other sectoral strategies, so as to achieve the maximum effect. The aim of the current survey is to determine the impact of digitalization on the level of competitiveness of viticulture enterprises.

KEYWORDS: digitalization, viticulture, competitiveness

ABSTRAKT

Derzeit verfügt Bulgarien über eine fertige und etablierte Strategie für die Digitalisierung der Landwirtschaft, aber es gibt keine solche Strategie für die Weinbauindustrie. Ich bin der Meinung, dass die Digitalisierungsstrategie für die Landwirtschaft in separate sektorale Strategien aufgeteilt werden sollte, wenn wir eine effektive sektorale Digitalisierungsstrategie im Sinne einer wettbewerbsfähigen Entwicklung erreichen wollen. Jeder Zweig der Landwirtschaft hat seine Besonderheiten, die sich in der Strategie für seine Digitalisierung widerspiegeln müssen, und jede der Strategien muss mit den anderen sektoralen Strategien ergänzt werden, um den maximalen Effekt zu erzielen. Ziel der vorliegenden Untersuchung ist es, die Auswirkungen der Digitalisierung auf die Wettbewerbsfähigkeit der Weinbaubetriebe zu ermitteln.

STICHWORTE: Digitalisierung, Weinbau, Wettbewerbsfähigkeit

RÉSUMÉ

À ce stade, la Bulgarie dispose d'une stratégie prête et établie pour la numérisation de l'agriculture, mais il n'existe pas de stratégie de ce type pour l'industrie viticole. Je pense que la stratégie de numérisation de l'agriculture devrait être décomposée en stratégies sectorielles distinctes si nous voulons une stratégie de numérisation sectorielle efficace en termes de développement compétitif. Chaque branche de l'agriculture a ses spécificités, qui doivent se refléter dans la stratégie de numérisation, et chacune des stratégies doit être complétée par les autres stratégies sectorielles, afin d'obtenir un effet maximal. L'objectif de la présente étude est de déterminer l'impact de la numérisation sur le niveau de compétitivité des entreprises viticoles.

MOTS-CLÉS: numérisation, viticulture, compétitivité

INTRODUCTION

The digitization of the viticulture sector is a phenomenon that is accelerating its development through generous government support, both at the European and national level. In recent years, European policy has been based on the idea that the sustainable development of agriculture can be achieved by observing the principles of circularity and utilizing the resources used in the production process in enterprises to the maximum extent [Stoeva, Dirimanova and Borisov, 2021]. Achieving the maximum degree of utilization of resources requires the faster and more joint digitization of processes, both at the sector level and at the farm level. The viticulture sector is also covered by the regulatory framework of the more inclusive digitalisation policy. It is one of the viticultural industries that generates products with high added value, traded both locally, as well as in the international market. An industry that generates a significant share of the gross added value in the "agriculture" sector and in which there is a large number of employees. Sustainable competitive development requires the imposition of perfect control over all business processes in the viticulture enterprise, which is only possible by imposing the digitization approach of these processes [Fidanska, Borisov and Nikolov, 2021]. Competitiveness increasingly relies on digitization and the skillful extraction of benefits from this process, benefits to be turned into a competitive advantage over other market participants. That is why I believe that a sectoral strategy for more joint digitization is needed, which will be a key competitive determining factor for the development of viticulture in our country. At this stage, Bulgaria has a ready and established strategy for digitization of agriculture, but there is no such strategy for the viticulture industry. I believe that the digitalization strategy of agriculture should be decomposed into separate sectoral strategies if we want an effective sectoral digitalization strategy in terms of achieving competitive development [Behluli, Qerimi, Borisov and Hajdari, 2020]. Each branch of agriculture has its specifics, which must be reflected in the strategy for its digitalization, and that each of the strategies must be complemented with the other sectoral strategies, so as to achieve the maximum effect [Borisov, 2021].

The aim of the current survey is to determine the impact of digitalization on the level of competitiveness of viticulture enterprises.

An approach to impact analysis and assessment. The process of drawing up a methodology for the analysis and assessment of the competitiveness of the wine-growing enterprise covers two main stages - (1) identification of indicators for the analysis and assessment of the competitiveness of the wine-growing enterprises and (2) validation of the indicators for assessing the competitiveness of viticultural enterprises. The main methods used in the compilation of the methodology are the method of multicriteria analysis and the method of expert evaluation. [Borisov and Garabedian, 2020]

Identification of markers and indicators for assessing the competitiveness of wine-growing enterprises. The identification of markers and indicators for brevity called - (indicators) for assessing competitiveness is carried out by multi-criteria analysis. A potential list of indicators has been prepared, which are evaluated by experts from various scientific and practical fields - economists, technologists - agronomists, managers and marketers. Based on their assessments, the final set of indicators was formed, which are used to assess the competitiveness of the wine-growing enterprises and the sector as a whole. The methodology is divided into different steps covering literature review, multi-criteria evaluation, selection of indicators, integration of indicators, field study, data analysis and applicability assessment. As

a result of a comprehensive literature review, a list of indicators is drawn up, taking into account the various aspects of competitiveness. A special place among them is occupied by:

- Indicators used by national and international institutions;
- Specific indicators (used in scientific literature);
- Indicators created by the authors of the presented methodology.

Table 1. Description of the criteria for expert evaluation of the proposed list of indicators for evaluating the competitiveness of viticulture enterprises. Source: adapted model of [Borisov, Stoeva and Dirimanova, 2021]

KES		Description
1 & 2	Distinctive power by (1) time / (2) place	The ability to reflect (1) time / (2) place differences due to external factors and those in management result
3	Analytical value	The indicator must be scientifically based, i.e. yes it is calculated using established scientific terms
4	Measurability	The indicator must Yes is easy for measurement. Therefore, its use is judged by the costs, which requires
5	Transparency	The meaning of the indicator should be clear to understand and unequivocally
6	Relevance	The indicator should help to account for the effect of the management of competitiveness factors
7	Transferability	The indicator should be able to be used in different types of business structures
8	Relevance	The indicator should be maximally relevant in terms of competitiveness, related to the database

In the case of the Multi-criteria expert evaluation (MKE), the confirmation of the potential indicators is carried out by experts. They are selected on the basis of their competence and commitment to solving problems related to the competitiveness of the viticulture sector. Indicators and experts are grouped thematically in panels forming the different aspects of competitiveness. The evaluation of the potential indicators by the experts is carried out according to eight principles included in the expert selection criteria (ESC) - table 1.

After agreeing to participate, the experts receive the following documents: a list of the characteristics of the indicators (name, stability in evaluation, description, source, calculation method, necessary information, rating scale and interpretation) and guidelines for the evaluation procedure. Based on these documents, the experts, according to their thematic affiliation, evaluate each indicator according to the eight principles (see table 1). Experts use a 4-point scale to rate the indicator in terms of relevance with each of the 8 principles as follows: 0 – not relevant, 1 – low degree of relevance, 2 – strong degree of relevance and 3 – very strong degree of relevance.

The reporting is based on a scale, where indicators that received expert evaluations above a given level are selected. The indicator selection criterion includes the expert's score for each indicator and the average score for the eight principles. The different evaluations of the experts for each indicator are synthesized in an "arithmetic mean value", formed as an expert consensus score, equal to the average weighted score obtained from the sum of all experts for a given indicator. The selected indicators are included in a questionnaire that is used in a test survey in selected agricultural enterprises.

Figure 1. Results of validation of competitiveness markers. Results are from a focus group conducted with 33 experts, survey - 2021.

Validation of markers and indicators for assessing the competitiveness of wine-growing enterprises. Figure 1 shows the assessment of the experts regarding the markers for the diagnosis of the competitiveness of wine-growing enterprises. The individual evaluations of the experts for each individual marker are synthesized in an "arithmetic mean value", formed as an expert consensus score (ECR), equal to the average weighted score obtained from the sum of all experts for a given marker. Competitiveness markers that received an EQF above 2.5 points are defined as reliable regarding the underlying principles in the validation of the indicators (see in the figure, the pillars in green). As reliable markers, experts have indicated - (1) the presence of sustainable competitive advantages – the value of the indicator is 3.00; (2) adaptability to change; (3) the preservation of market power; (4) a unique value proposition; (5) efficiency

of the resources used; (6) labor productivity; (7) access to new markets: (8) diversification of the product range.

Figure 2 shows the summary expert assessment regarding the reliability of the indicators of competitiveness of wine-growing enterprises. Out of all 14 indicators, the experts have validated as reliable - 6. The results of the expert evaluation show that the following indicators are highly reliable for the diagnosis of the viticulture: (1) market share dynamics - with a value of 3.00; (2) profitability of sales - with a value of 2.6; (3) return on investment - with a value of 2.6; (4) gross margin with a value of 2.5; (5) competitive advantage index with a value of 2.5 and (6) direct cost effectiveness – a value of 2.5.

Figure 2. Results of validation of competitiveness indicators. Results are from a focus group conducted with 33 experts, survey - 2021.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact analysis and assessment. The assessment of the impact of digitalization on the degree of competitiveness is based on the results of a survey conducted among 30 agricultural enterprises, whose owners have to some extent implemented digital technologies in the management of the activity. Of the surveyed agricultural enterprises, 75% have managed to implement several hardware solutions and related software. Which, based on the conducted field research, is defined as a high level of digitization of management activities. Of all agricultural enterprises, 33% use software for processing agricultural information, as an element of digitization applicable in the daily management of the viticulture enterprise, and 13% have relied only on a single hardware solution.

Subjective analysis of the effects of digitalization on the level of competitiveness of wine-growing enterprises. In the course of conducting a survey, the owners assess to what extent the digital

solutions used influence the level of competitiveness of the agricultural enterprises they own. Competitiveness is assessed through the indicators - profitability of sales, return on investments and gross margin. These indicators through a pilot study among wineries are defined as recognizable by the owners. The self-assessment approach is used regarding the results achieved from the application of digital solutions.

Figure 3. Impact of digitalization on the profitability of sales in viticulture enterprises. Results of a field study among 30 enterprises, 2021-2022.

The results of the survey indicate that with a high degree of implementation of digital solutions in the management of the vineyard, the profitability of sales increases - 75% of the surveyed farmers state this as a fact. Businesses that have implemented only a single hardware solution and related software also report an increase in the profitability of sales - 77% of the surveyed owners say that the profitability of the sales made increases (see figure 3).

Figure 4. Impact of digitalization on the return on investment in viticulture enterprises. Results of a field study among 30 enterprises, 2021-2022.

The effects of digitization on the return on investment made are generally also positively assessed by the owners. Owners who have implemented a large number of hardware solutions and related software are of the opinion that this solution of theirs has had a critical effect on the return on investment inviticulture - 50% of them declare that profitability has increased. The share of owners (60% of all respondents) who own enterprises in which the implementation of a single hardware and related software solution leads to an increasing return on investment is also significant.

The following figure shows the evaluation of the owners regarding the application of digital solutions in the management of the farm. The data shows that the gross margin increases mostly with the implementation of a higher degree of digitization in the management of the wine-growing enterprise – 50% of the surveyed owners indicate that the gross margin has increased (see figure 4). In 60% of the surveyed owners, it is noticed that when implementing only software for processing agricultural information, the gross margin remains unchanged. One 25% of the owners state that with the digitization of farm management, the gross margin decreases over time.

Figure 5. Impact of digitalization on the gross margin in wine-growing enterprises. Results of a field study among 30 enterprises, 2021-2022.

Regression analysis of the effects of digitalization on the level of competitiveness of wine-growing enterprises. Through the regression analysis, the aim is to establish to what extent there is a statistically significant relationship between the costs incurred for digitization of the management of the viticultural economy (these costs are perceived as a factorial indicator) and its level of competitiveness, which it achieves as a result [Borisov and Radev, 2020]. As performance indicators evaluating the effects

of the degree of digitization of the management of the wine-growing enterprise are used - (1) return on investments; (2) gross profit; (3) sales revenue; (4) gross margin; (5) profitability of sales and (6) market share. All these indicators have undergone validation and can be considered reliable in assessing the level of competitiveness achieved. 6 relationships between the indicators characterizing the cause factor and the result factor are tested as follows [Petrov and Borisov, 2021]]:

- Relationship between precision technology implementation costs and return on investment;
- Relationship between precision technology implementation costs and gross profit;
- Relationship between precision technology implementation costs and sales revenue;
- Relationship between precision technology implementation costs and gross margin;
- Relationship between precision technology implementation costs and sales profitability;
- Relationship between precision technology implementation costs and market share.

Table 2. Results of a regression analysis assessing the interaction between the degree of digitalization and the level of competitiveness of wine-growing enterprises. Source: own.

Statistical indicators	Return on investment	Gross profit	Sales revenue	Gross margin	Return on sales	Market share
Correlation coefficient	0.174	0.935	0.095	0.304	0.776	0.095
Multiple R						
Coefficient of definition	0.030	0.875	0.0091	0.093	0.603	0.009
R square						
Adjusted R Square	-0.004	0.871	-0.0261	0.060	0.589	-0.026
Degree of dependence	weak	very strong	very weak	moderate	strong	very weak
Type of addiction	negative	positive	negative	positive	positive	negative
Regression coefficient b0	0.788	18805.9	6208280.2	620901.2	0.034	3.44
Regression coefficient b1	-1.797	0.05	-0.0431	-1.4313	00000.5	-2.4

Table 2 gives the results of testing the relationship between the degree of digitalization and the achieved level of competitiveness of wine-growing enterprises. The performed regression analysis proves that the costs of implementing precision technologies have a positive (there is a direct relationship between the studied factors) influence on the gross profit and the profitability of sales. A strong degree of dependence is noticeable in these two investigated relationships – the coefficients of determination are -0.875 and 0.603, respectively. Expenditure on precision technology has a negative impact on the return on investment, sales revenue, gross margin and market share of the wine industry.

CONCLUSIONS

Digitization in the viticulture sector is in its infancy. Viticulture and wine enterprises have mainly managed to digitize their accounting and supply activities. They have partly managed to digitize some critical technological phases of the production process such as irrigation and monitoring of the vineyard, control and monitoring of the distillation process.

The challenges associated with the application of precision agriculture in the industry can be divided into two broad areas: (1) those inherent in the technological means used in precision agriculture (drones, robots, GPS, etc.), raising questions of technological control, human safety, civil liability and

privacy, and (2) those emerging alongside the development of precision agriculture as an autonomous technological field.

The lack of rural broadband infrastructure and connectivity to devices (eg a tractor, computer, tablet or smartphone that records what is happening, or a device for privacy issues of satellite photography) providing access and ownership of data is one of the main problems for the accelerated implementation of the precision agriculture approach in the industry.

When applying the precision agriculture approach in the industry, some serious problems arise related to the compatibility between agricultural equipment and digital infrastructure. Among the entrepreneurial community, there is concern about hardware and software compatibility, as well as how to choose the right technical systems to implement precision agriculture. It is important that the various digital technologies that will be used in the enterprise are compatible with the hardware devices in which the entrepreneur has invested. Buying the necessary hardware devices is an expensive investment, and if these devices do not have the necessary compatibility with the software needed to solve the daily problems of farms, then this will make the investment itself meaningless;

The results of the survey indicate that with a high degree of implementation of digital solutions in the management of the wine-growing enterprise, the profitability of sales increases - 75% of the surveyed wine-growing producers state this as a fact. Businesses that implemented only a single hardware solution and related software also reported an increase in profitability of sales - 77% of surveyed owners said that profitability of sales made increased

The effects of digitization on the return on investment made are generally also positively assessed by the owners. Owners who have implemented a large number of hardware solutions and related software are of the opinion that this decision of theirs has had a critical effect on the return on investment in the winery - 50% of them declare that the return has increased. The share of owners (60% of total respondents) who own enterprises in which the implementation of a single hardware and related software solution leads to an increasing return on investment is also significant.

As a result of the conducted statistical research, it can be summarized that digitalization has an impact on the competitiveness of the wine-growing enterprise in terms of an increase in gross profit and profitability of sales. Digitization, expressed through the level of costs for its implementation in the viticulture enterprise, has a systematic negative impact on the return on investment, sales revenue and gross margin.

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